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Tax Sheltering Attributes and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated tax sheltering attributes and corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. Using effective tax rate (ETR), book-tax difference (BTD) and temporary tax difference (TTD) as proxy of tax sheltering attributes with control variables such as operating cash flow (OPC), financial leverage (FLVR), and firm age (LFAGE) and total investment expenditure as proxy of corporate investment expenditure. *Ex-post facto* research design was employed, data used were sourced from published annual reports and accounts of listed financial firms in Nigeria, covering the forty-nine (49) financial services firms in Nigeria as of 31st December 2022. Using purposive sampling techniques, ten (10) commercial banks, two (2) mortgage banks and eight (8) firms from insurance and reinsurance sector that have been actively operating from 2012-2022. Data were analysed using descriptive analysis, pearson correlation, and other diagnostic tests such as, stationarity and cointegration, heteroskedasticity, model Mis, VIF, serial autocorrelation and hausman test and panel regression analysis. the findings revealed that effective tax rate exerted a statistically significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure, unit change in the book tax difference will increase corporate investment and temporary book-tax difference (TBD) exerted a significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. The study recommends among others that effective tax rates of the financial firms should be monitored in relation to the statutory tax rate to ensure that it does not increase significantly.

Keywords: Book-tax difference, Corporate investment expenditure, Effective tax rate, Financial leverage, Operating cash flow, Tax sheltering, temporary tax-book difference.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Established management literature, specifically agency theory, posits that corporate executives should prioritize maximizing firm value for shareholder benefit (Jensen & Meckling, 1976, as cited in Nicholson & Kiel, 2004). The story has shifted considering new research on corporate governance and sustainability, two areas that have emerged as central to modern theories of corporate management. Businesses today are expected to generate long-term value for all stakeholders (Karami & Rekabdar, 2020; Igbru et al 2015; Ogbo et al, 2026). Managers of these companies should prioritise the interests of all stakeholders (Ingrid, 2017; Udochukwu et al., 2022). Corporate managers, according to this stakeholder approach, should treat their company's internal and external stakeholders fairly. Tax sheltering comprises a wide range of acts with the express objective to lower tax (expenses) burden. (Dyrenge & Maydew, 2018; Martinez et al., 2019, Obasi, et al., 2020, Anyaduba & Ogbeide, 2022; Delgado et al., 2023). Tax sheltering is a legitimate activity if it is undertaken within

the range of the law (Obasi et al. 2020, Ogbo et al, 2026). For an organization to implement efficient tax planning or sheltering practices, the managers must be knowledgeable in tax law and administration, audit and have expertise. In the view of Bonner et al. (1992) in Kpportorgbi et al. (2018) the managers must possess cognitive skills and personal dispositions. These skills include that the managers must be able to understand the tax legislation; discover (opportunity) gaps in the tax law, define consistent and successive plans to exploit the opportunities, and implement the scheme. Previous studies have employed numerous financial statement indicators to estimate the amount of tax avoidance in corporate organizations. Though, many have voiced concerns that the saving of money from taxes may lead to agency cost problems as opportunistic managers exploit the loophole for personal gains. Igbru, et al, (2017), business investment is a key engine of economic growth in many economies and taxation has a large effect on a firm's investment decisions. However, the amount to which corporation taxation influences company investment is primarily an unsettled subject in economics (Moon, 2019). Therefore, this study is an attempt to answer this question by presenting empirical evidence from a Nigeria financial services organisation.

Generally, the difference in interest's from the government is to expect huge and consistently increasing tax revenues each year, and of course opposite to the interests of corporations that want to pay as minimum tax as possible. Consequently, company managers do engage in numerous strategic tax planning efforts. They have been named tax sheltering, tax avoidance, tax planning, tax minimization or tax aggression in the legal form or tax evasion in the fraudulent aspect. From this perspective, these activities capture two limitations, tax preferred transactions (legal practices) on one end and aggressive behaviours (illegal practices) on the other end, throwing up complexity in determining practices that are legal, optimal and illegal.

In Nigeria, businesses are challenged with the issues of various taxations, ineffective administrative tax systems, high tax rates, unfriendly tax laws and other operating expenditures that endanger their survival and the going-concern status of their operations. Resultantly, a considerable corpus of tax accounting literature has arisen, over the last decades. Most of these studies focused heavily on the non-financial sector like manufacturing sector. There is a scarcity of empirical evidence from the financial sector which is one of the majors of the economy. Again, the question relating to the degree to which cash flow from tax sheltering enhances company investment expenditure has been highlighted. These identified gaps in empirical investigations are the impetus for our study. The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of tax sheltering on corporate investment expenditure. However, the specific objectives are to: Ascertain the effect of effective tax rate, book-tax difference, and temporary book-tax difference on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Effective Tax Rate (ETR)

The effective tax rate can also be referred to as the IFRS effective tax rate (ETR). The effective tax rate is derived by dividing total tax expenses by income before tax, revealing the proportion of accounting income that is taxed (Chen et al., 2010; Dyreng et al., 2010; Salihu et al., 2013). It also measures the average tax rate per unit of profits. The adoption of an effective tax rate demonstrates firms' extensive tax preparation via lasting book-tax differences. According to Lee et al. (2015), comparing the computed IFRS (ETR) to the statutory rate or a control rate to measure tax aggressiveness indicates the level of tax hiding. They claim that the IFRS (ETR) indicates permanent book-tax differences from statutory corrections since total income tax expenses contain both current and deferred tax expenses. According to the Companies Income Tax Act (CITA), Cap C21, LFN 2004 (as amended), the statutory tax rate for Nigerian companies having a turnover of more than one hundred million (#100 million) naira is 30%. Section 40(1) of the Act allows for a 20% tax on firms with a turnover of more than twenty-five (N25 million) naira but less than one hundred (N100 million) naira, and a 0% tax on companies with a turnover of less than twenty-five (N25 million). Some scholars have further proxies effective tax rate using income tax expense divided by operating cash flow, the ratio of cash taxes paid to operating cash flow, effective tax rate (ETR) differentials, and current reported tax divided by profit before tax (Desai & Dharmapala, 2008; Chen et al., 2010;

Aliani & Zarai, 2012; Zemzem & Flouhi, 2013; Bousaidi & Hamed, 2015; Oyeleke et al., 2016). This study proxy effective tax rate as follows:

$$ETR = \frac{\text{Total tax expenses}}{\text{Profit before tax}}$$

Drawing from the reviewed literature, the following hypothesis was formulated: effective tax rate has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure. of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Book-Tax Difference

The book-tax difference, developed by Manzon and Plesko (2002) and supported by Desai and Dharmapala (2009), is primarily estimated using financial statement data and focuses on the amount of the discrepancy between accounting income and taxable income. It is the most complete metric, capturing both temporary and permanent book-tax differences. Although the causes of book-tax difference (BTD) vary and are typically classified as permanent or temporary discrepancies, the size of the gap reflects the prevalence of tax evasion strategies (Kim et al., 2011). According to Rego (2003), tax-aggressive operations can result in book-tax disparities, which are temporary or permanent discrepancies between a company's financial accounting and taxable revenue. In this study, we used the book-tax gap to reflect the level of tax sheltering operations in Nigeria, which was measured as follows:

$$\text{Book Tax Difference} = \frac{\text{Profit Tax} - \text{Tax Expenses}}{\text{Statutory Tax Rate}}$$

Based on the insights from the literature reviewed, the following hypothesis was formulated: Book-tax difference does not react to corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Temporary Tax Difference

Temporary tax difference refers to the disparities that arise because of variances between book and taxable income, which are related to the period of accumulated income and expense items (Sulistyowati & Hendrawati, 2018). This temporal difference arises from the timing of the acknowledgment of sales and costs in the computation of profits (Resmi, 2014; Sulistyowati & Hendrawati, 2018). It provides future impact over a set period, resulting in an equal effect on accounting and fiscal profit. It is expected to provide information on the prospective management of non-tax accruals such as depreciation (Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010). The temporary book-to-tax gap is the differential tax expenses multiplied by the applicable statutory rate (Igburu & Orife, 2024). However, we defined TBD as a variable in this study as follows:

$$\text{Temporary Tax Difference} = \frac{\text{Deferred Tax}}{\text{Corporate Statutory Tax Rate}}$$

Based on the foregoing literature reviewed, the following hypothesis was formulated: temporary book-tax difference does not respond to corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Corporate Investment Expenditure

According to Osegbue et al. (2021), business investment is the allocation of funds with the expectation of a future benefit. They believe that the influx of capital investments is influenced by a variety of factors such as taxation, legal and regulatory frameworks, and the degree of openness, among others. Corporate investment, according to them, is a driver of technological innovation, infrastructural development, wealth creation, employment and empowerment, and a rise in people's standard of living and social well-being in an economy. According to Moon (2019), one of the most pressing economic concerns is the extent to which corporate taxes affect company investment. According to Adegbite and Shittu (2017), the sensitivity of corporate taxation to business investment varies depending on a country's tax laws, tax policies, and tax incentives, which is especially true in Nigeria, where taxation is being adjusted (Osegbue et al., 2021).

Theoretical Review

Tax Planning Theory

William Hoffman proposed tax planning theory in 1961, claiming that taxpayers can organise their financial activities to incur the lowest possible tax burden through effective tax planning. According to William Hoffman, not all tax strategies reduce the tax burden to the targeted minimum. He argues that not tailoring tax planning to individual taxpayers might lead to unfavourable tax outcomes.

According to Kumbour et al. (2017), there are generally four requirements for effective tax planning activities. They say that tax planning comprises predicting scenarios and identifying loopholes (opportunities) in existing tax law to reduce or defer tax. As a result, the assumption for effective tax planning includes proficiency in understanding tax law, the ability to identify opportunities in the prevailing tax law, the ability to devise a strategy to capitalise on the identified opportunities, and the ability to implement the strategy in the form of company policies. According to Bonner et al. (1992), as mentioned in Kportorgbi and Gadzo (2018), this series of events necessitates cognitive skills and a certain personal disposition. As a result, tax planning theory is critical to this work since it represents the skill level required for successful tax avoidance activities. According to Ogbeide and Iyafekhe (2018), tax saving is often associated with tax planning, but it can take other forms. According to Hoffman (1961) tax planning activity theories generate ideas and philosophies that are generally applicable to tax practitioners. As a result, a tax plan cannot be permanent or continued for an extended period unless the tax planning acts are "flexible," implying tactic continuity. However, the current restriction should be further lowered to meet the future needs of taxpayers.

Empirical Review

Delgado et al. (2023) used artificial neural network regressions to examine the relationship between tax avoidance and profit management in the five largest European Union economies. They used a dataset from the Compustat database covering the years 2006 to 2015. The study's independent variables were the effective tax rate (split into GAAP and CASH tax rates) and book-tax disparities, whereas the dependent variable was discretionary accruals. The findings show nonlinear patterns and a positive, statistically significant relationship between discretionary accruals and both ETR indicators, implying that when companies use earnings management, they will have a higher taxable income, higher ETR, and less tax avoidance. Gilang and Wahya (2022) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility on tax avoidance. Agency theory was used to explain the link between corporate social responsibility characteristics and tax aggression. The study employed a variety of panel data regression techniques: The findings indicate that corporate social responsibility has a negative and considerable impact on tax aggressiveness. This demonstrates that firms strive to avoid tax evasion and comply more strictly with applicable tax legislation in order to improve their reputation as loyal taxpayers. In Portugal, Pereira et al. (2022) sought to determine if book-tax disparities continue to impair earning persistence in the age of information technology and strict compliance monitoring. They chose 421 small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) between 2016 and 2020 to achieve this goal. The study also used book-tax differences, which recognise the existence of both taxable and deductible transitory differences. To test these assumptions, they ran economic regressions on panel data. The findings revealed that earning persistence decreases as deductible temporary differences increase, whereas taxable temporary differences had no statistically significant effect. Similarly, Olurankinse and Mamidu (2021) examined the relationship between tax planning and the financial performance of Nigeria's development banks from 2012 to 2019. The study used return on equity as a measure of financial success, effective tax rate and tax savings as explanatory variables, and capital intensity and firm size as controls. The data was analysed using multiple panel data OLS regression. The results show that the effect of effective tax rate and tax savings was statistically non-significant on return on equity, whereas capital-intensiveness and business size had a positive statistically significant influence on return on equity. Muhammad et al. (2020) published empirical data on the influence of tax aggressiveness and management ownership on firm value. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the data. The outcome of this research indicated that Firm Value did not influence tax aggressiveness listed on Bursa Efek Indonesia (BEI), but Managerial Ownership affects tax aggressiveness listed on Bursa Efek Indonesia (BEI). Estralita et al. (2020) used data from 2015 to 2017 to produce empirical evidence on the impact of accounting errors on tax aggressiveness using control factors such as leverage and profitability in the period before and after the tax amnesty. This study used SPSS version 23 and Smart PLS3 to analyse data from all industrial businesses with purposive samples between 2015 and 2017. This investigation shows that accounting errors had little influence on tax evasion in the period before and after the tax amnesty. In Nigeria, Ogunmakin et al. (2020) evaluated the relationship between tax evasion and the financial performance of listed firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) from 2006 to 2014. The study looked at performance in terms of earnings per share, with profit before tax (PBT), debt-equity

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

<i>stats</i>	<i>tie</i>	<i>ime</i>	<i>Etr</i>	<i>Btd</i>	<i>tbd</i>	<i>ocf</i>	<i>flvr</i>	<i>Infa</i>
Summary Stats								
Minimum	0.0102	0.0009	-7.9583	-0.2339	-0.1680	-0.1884	0.1277	0.0000
Maximum	0.4459	0.0468	0.8809	0.1486	0.404	0.4505	1.6616	4.654
Mean	0.0992	0.0066	0.0768	0.0156	0.0098	0.0429	0.6883	3.3209
Median	0.0559	0.0046	0.1466	0.0123	0.0036	0.0407	0.8143	3.3673
Standard Deviation (SD)	0.0977	0.0058	0.6181	0.0376	0.0685	0.0890	0.2365	0.8127
SE(Mean)	0.0066	0.0004	0.0417	0.0025	0.0046	0.0060	0.0159	0.0548
Normality Test								
Skewness	1.8793	3.5142	-10.6890	-0.7137	2.5138	0.6922	0.4065	-1.5951
Pr(Skewness)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0142	0.0000
Kurtosis	5.8621	21.8061	134.0882	13.3242	13.4568	5.8443	3.3499	6.7422
Pr(Kurtosis)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.2357	0.0000
----- joint -----								
chi2(2)	64.1700	-	-	51.2900	-	27.7100	7.0200	59.4100
Prob>chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0299	0.0000
Shapiro-Wilk W test (Prob>z)	0.0000							

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.1 depicts the summary of descriptive statistics conducted on the data. The “Overall” statistics are ordinary statistics that are based on 220 observations. The mean and the median of the ten (10) variables, the powerful statistical measures of mid-point even though vulnerable to extreme values of the listed twenty (20) financial firms in Nigeria in two hundred and twenty (220) observations were computed. The closeness between the mean and median in almost all the variables particularly the explanatory variables suggest the existence of uniformity in the performance of the financial firms in Nigeria which indicates that the disparity in the sizes of the firms has no effect on their tax management performance, indicating no material extreme values.

On the other hand, the standard deviation, a measure of dispersion is not large suggesting that annual values of each of the variables are very close to the mid-point.

Pairwise Correlations

Table 4.2. Correlation Matrix with P-values involving 220 Observations

	<i>tie</i>	<i>ime</i>	<i>Etr</i>	<i>btd</i>	<i>tbd</i>	<i>ocf</i>	<i>flvr</i>	<i>Infa</i>
<i>tie</i>	1.0000							
<i>ime</i>	0.7190*	1.0000						
	0.0000							
<i>etr</i>	-0.1011	-0.2252*	1.0000					
	0.1350	0.0008						
<i>btd</i>	0.0246	-0.0093	0.0987	1.0000				
	0.7170	0.8910	0.1445					
<i>tbd</i>	-0.1783*	-0.2915*	-0.0784	-0.0307	1.0000			
	0.0080	0.0000	0.2466	0.6501				
<i>ocf</i>	-0.1923*	-0.0806	0.1425*	0.1076	-0.0033	1.0000		
	0.0042	0.2339	0.0346	0.1115	0.9614			
<i>flvr</i>	-0.7467*	-0.6223*	0.1165	-0.1350*	0.2827*	0.1403*	1.0000	
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0848	0.0455	0.0000	0.0376		
<i>Infa</i>	0.1695*	0.2247*	-0.1304	0.0208	0.2597*	-0.0612	-0.1225	1.0000
	0.0118	0.0008	0.0534	0.7586	0.0001	0.3662	0.0697	

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.2 portrays a significant relationship between five (5) predictor variables (temporary book tax difference, permanent book tax difference, operating cash flows all deflated by total assets financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age and total investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. Precisely, the temporary book tax difference, operating cash flows, and financial leverage depicts a negative significant relationship while the permanent book tax difference and natural logarithm of firm age displayed a positive significant connection with total investment maintenance expenditure. However, the association between effective tax rate, book tax difference and tax savings are non-significant. On the hand, the effective tax rate, temporary book tax difference, permanent book tax difference, financial leverage and the natural logarithm of firm age displayed a strong association with investment maintenance expenditure. Effective tax rate, temporary book tax difference and financial leverage have strong negative association with investment maintenance expenditure while permanent book tax and the natural logarithm of firm age exhibited a strong positive relationship with investment expenditure. However, the relationship between the investment maintenance expenditure and book tax rate, tax savings and operating cash flows are non-significant.

Table 4.3 Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root test Based on Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests

Variables	Unadjusted t	Adjusted t*	p-value	Lags
	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>ADF regressions</i>
Tie	-24.8551	-18.7304	0.0000	3
lme	-11.8000	-4.0483	0.0001	1
Etr	-16.0771	-10.6635	0.0153	3
Btd	-20.9004	-15.8683	0.0000	1
Tbd	-9.0744	-6.9029	0.0000	1
Ocf	-15.5848	-8.4760	0.0000	1
Flvr	-36.2706	-33.5206	0.0000	3
Lnage	-14.1844	-11.2943	0.0000	1

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.3 depicts the outcome of the Levin-Lin Chu unit-root test based on augmented Dickey-Fuller tests carried out on the data at lag 1 to 3. The results of this test statistics strongly reject the null hypothesis that the panels contain unit-roots for all the entered variables at lag 1-3. Therefore, we conclude that the data for all variables in the study are stationary.

Diagnostic Test for Heteroskedasticity

Table 4.4: Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity (All-Inclusive Model)

Ho: Constant variance			
Variables: fitted values of	tieta	tieta	imeta
chi2(1)	=	116.74	207.47
Prob > chi2	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.4 depicts the Breusch-Pagan test result for heteroskedasticity for the model specification. Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test was employed to ascertain whether the standard deviation of the data over the period is statistically constant (heteroskedasticity problem). Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test assumes the p-value of above the significant levels to be free from heteroskedasticity problem among the datasets. In this case, the result shows a Prob>chi2 = 0.0000 which is very significant. This result signifies the presence of a heteroskedasticity problem on the dataset. If this is not corrected, it leads to biased standard errors.

Test for Model Mis – Specification

Table 4.5: Ramsey RESET Mis-specification Test

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of eps			
Ho: model has no omitted variables			
		Tieta	imeta
F(3, 208)	=	18.01	18.57
Prob > F	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.5 presents the outcome of Ramsey Reset test used to ascertain if the comprehensive model is appropriately specified i.e. over or underfit. The reset test implies acceptance of the null hypothesis that the model has no omitted variables. The result of these test shows $F(3, 208) = 18.01$ & 18.57 with P-values (0.0000) which implies that the model is not over-specified. Alternatively, the result could be ascertained manually by truncating a few independent variables and estimating another regression and visual examination of the old and new (full) residuals for $F_{calc} < F(3, 208)$ using the formula.

$$F_{calc} = \frac{(R^2_{new} - R^2_{old}) / \text{number of new predictors}}{(1 - R^2_{new}) / (n - \text{number of betas in the new model})}$$

Test for multi-collinearity

Multicollinearity is an unsteady condition of the regression model, estimates, and over-bloated standard errors for the coefficient (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). They further stated that it usually emanated from model specification, data collection methods, restrictions in the population and sample size, and the common trend of the regressors over time. The variance inflation factor measures the degree of the (strong) linear relationship between one predictor variable and one or more explanatory variables. As a rule of thumb, Montgomery and Peck (2007) suggested $5 < VIF < 10$. This implies that VIFs value between 1 and 5 is moderate but above 5 is severe.

Table 4.6: Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Btd	10.58	0.000004
Tbd	8.23	0.000004
Flvr	1.21	0.825739
Lnfa	1.14	0.877631
Etr	1.08	0.924181
Ocf	1.06	0.944081
Mean VIF		4.35

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

A test of multicollinearity was conducted using the variance inflation factor approach (VIF) as depicted in Table 4.6. In this instance, the explanatory variables have resultant variance inflation factors ranging between 1.06 and 10.58 and a mean VIF of $4.35 < 5.0$ for the comprehensive model. These results indicate the presence of severe multicollinearity problems connected to book tax difference deflated by the total assets and tax savings to total assets but moderate multicollinearity between the explanatory (independent) variables in the regression model which is acceptable. Nonetheless, in case of severe multicollinearity problem, Gujarati and Porter (2009) posit that it is likely to be resolved by removing one or more variables, employing a priori information from theory, transforming variables, adding new data, and principal components analysis or by employing factor analysis and ridge regression among others.

Fixed Effects Vs Random Effects Tests of Model Estimation

Table 4.7: Hausman Test of All-Inclusive Model Validity

Variable	(b) fe	(B) Re	(b-B) Difference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
etr	-0.005144	-0.006203	0.001059	0.045259
btd	-3.455404	4.031168	-7.486572	0.163525
tbd	-110.1463	-142.2445	32.09825	0.019358
ocf	0.0281372	0.0235908	0.0045464	0.030029
flvr	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	0.0844565	0.0059191
lnfa	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	-0.0158186	0.0040423

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg
 B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\chi^2(8) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^{-1}](b-B) = 129.44$$

$$\text{Prob}>\chi^2 = 0.0000$$

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.7 facilitates a choice between the *Fixed Effects Model (FEM)* and the *Random Effects Model (REM)*. The Hausman test has the null hypothesis that the preferred model is fixed effects vs the alternative fixed effect. The Hausman test results show $\chi^2(8) = 129.44$ and $\text{Prob.}>\chi^2 = 0.0000$ which suggest that the fixed effect model is not appropriate therefore strengthens the decision that the *Random Effect Model (REM)* is the most appropriate model for the panel dataset.

Model Estimation

The random effect (RE) regression model assumes that the variation across entities is random and uncorrelated with the predictor or regressor included in the model.

The random-effects model equation is:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_k X_{it} + \alpha_i + u_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where: α_i ($i = 1 \dots 20$) is the unknown intercept for each entity (20 firm-specific intercepts), Y_{it} is the regressand (TIE), i represents the firms (1- 20) and t is the time series (2012-2022), X_{it} represents the independent and control variables, β_k is the coefficients for independent and control variables, u_{it} is the Between-firms error term, and ε_{it} represents the Within-firms error term.

Table 4.8: Panel Regression Results of Tax Sheltering Indicators, Control Variables and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial firms in Nigeria

Regressors		Method	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effect	Random Effect (Recommended Model)	PCSEs (Preferred Model)
etr	p-value		0.779	0.202	0.178	0.000*
	t-statistic		0.28	-1.28	-1.35	-3.61
	coefficient		-0.0020655	-0.005144	-0.006203	-0.0026085
btd	p-value		0.888	0.887	0.885	0.026*
	t-statistic		0.14	-0.14	0.14	2.23
	coefficient		6.463275	-3.455404	4.031168	11.60817
tbd	p-value		0.488	0.174	0.126	0.000*
	t-statistic		-0.69	-1.36	1.53	-4.48
	coefficient		-106.2525	-110.1463	-0142.2445	-79.70631
ocf	p-value		0.081	0.315	0.426	0.152
	t-statistic		-1.75	1.01	0.74	-1.43
	coefficient		-0.0886617	0.0281372	0.0235908	-0.0113669
flvr	p-value		0.000*	0.001*	0.000*	0.000*
	t-statistic		-14.97	-3.36	-7.30	-18.51
	coefficient		-0.3049537	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	-0.1652166
lnfa	p-value		0.11	0.062	0.979	0.000*
	t-statistic		1.61	-1.88	-0.03	6.19
	coefficient		0.0092339	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	.0102448
_cons	p-value		0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000
	t-statistic		10.95	6.64	7.02	22.42
	Coefficient		0.2848017	0.2054517	0.2121882	.177882

<i>R-Squared</i>	57.67	0.2615	0.5479	0.3877
<i>F-statistic (Prob)/ Wald chi2 (Prob)</i>	35.93 (0.0000)	3.31(0.0015)	59.16 (0.0000)	38.06 (0.0000)
<i>rho (fraction of variance due to u_i)</i>		.87062491	.49943843	
<i>Poolability Test (Breusch-Pagan LM)</i>			340 (0.0000)	
<i>Hausman test</i>		129.44 (0.0000)		
<i>Original Durbin-Watson statistic</i>		2.04		
<i>No of Observations = 220</i>		<i>Number of Firms = 20</i>		

*Dependent Variable: KCE, significant at *1%, **5%, t-statistics*

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

From the statistics table above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.3877. In specific terms, it suggests that 38.77% of changes in total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressors (*effective tax rate, book tax difference, temporary book tax difference, operating cash flows, financial leverage, and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 38.06 and Prob. = 0.0000 are lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 38.77% explanatory power of the regressors is statistically significant in explaining changes in the total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Hence, this model is best fitted to explain the relationship between the regressors and the regressand included in the model. However, five (5) regressors (*effective tax rate, book tax difference, temporary book tax difference, financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age*) exhibited significant effect on the total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria as can be deduced from the coefficient and *p-values* $0.0000 < 0.05$. Operating cash flows exhibited somewhat non-significant effect on the total investment expenditure.

Robust Tests of the Model

Robust tests were carried out using investment maintenance expenditure as the regressand.

Table 4.9: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) using Investment Maintenance Expenditure (IME) as the Regressand

Panel-corrected						
<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coef.</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>P> z </i>	<i>[95% Conf.</i>	<i>Interval]</i>
Etr	-0.000722	0.000275	2.62	0.009	-0.001261	-0.000182
Btd	-0.621013	1.783506	0.35	0.728	-4.116620	2.874595
Tbd	-16.911630	6.767604	2.50	0.012	-30.175890	-3.647370
Ocf	0.001429	0.002398	0.60	0.551	-0.003270	0.006129
Flvr	-0.006772	0.002319	2.92	0.004	-0.011317	-0.002226
Lnfa	0.001651	0.000479	3.45	0.001	0.000712	0.002590
_cons	0.006274	0.001768	3.55	0.000	0.002808	0.009739

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

The summarized results of the robustness check conducted using investment maintenance expenditure as the regressand are depicted in Table 4.9. From the statistics table above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.2538. In specific terms, it suggests that 25.38% of changes in investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressors (*effective tax rate, book tax difference, temporary book tax difference, operating cash flows, financial leverage and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 28.93 and Prob. = 0.0003 are lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 25.38% explanatory power of the regressors is statistically significant in explaining changes in the investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Hence, this model is best fitted to explain the relationship between the regressors and the regressand included in the model.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 4.10: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) of Tax Sheltering Indicators and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

Panel-corrected						
Variables	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Etr	-0.000606	0.000112	-5.40	0.000	-0.000826	-0.000386
Btd	-0.449181	0.788712	-0.57	0.569	-1.995028	1.096666
Tbd	-12.272100	3.264527	-3.76	0.000	-18.670460	-5.873744
Ocf	0.000485	0.001346	0.36	0.718	-0.002152	0.003123
Flvr	-0.005318	0.000762	-6.98	0.000	-0.006812	-0.003824
Lnfa	0.001312	0.000253	5.18	0.000	0.000816	0.001809
_cons	0.006238	0.000903	6.91	0.000	0.004469	0.008008

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

H₀₁: Effective tax rate has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

As presented in table 4.10, the *Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) Model adjusted Autocorrelation (AR 1) statistics, Panel-level heteroskedastic and correlated across panels* were used to test the above-stated hypothesis. From table 4.10, the coefficient (β) indicates that a unit change in account effective tax rate will translate to -0.000606 increases in the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Specifically, effective tax rate exhibited a very strong negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the firms with a p-value = 0.000. However, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that effective tax rate exerted a statistically significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria, since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.000, and t-statistic < |2| at -5.40.

H₀₂: Book tax difference has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

As presented in table 4.10, the *Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) Model adjusted Autocorrelation (AR 1) statistics, Panel-level heteroskedastic and correlated across panels* was used to test the above-stated hypothesis. In respect of the coefficient (β), table 4.10 above indicates that a unit change in the book tax difference will increase corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria by -0.449150. Precisely, the book tax difference demonstrated a very weak negative effect on corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria with a p-value = 0.569. Since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.569, and t-statistic > |2| at -0.57, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that corporate investment expenditure does not respond significantly to changes in book tax difference of the listed financial firms in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Temporary book-tax difference has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Regarding the coefficient (β), table 4.10 above indicates that a unit change in the temporary book-tax difference (TBD) will increase the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria by -12.272106. Precisely, this variable exhibited a very strong negative influence on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria with a p-value = 0.000. Since the p-value < 0.05 at 0.000, and t-statistic < |2| at -3.76, we accept the alternate hypothesis and conclude that the temporary book-tax difference (TBD) exerted a significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, there is clear evidence to affirm that the indicators of tax sheltering activities modeled in this study *ETR, BTD, TBD*, and the control variables (OCF, FLVR and LnFA) have a very significant explanatory power to explain the variations in corporate investment expenditure and investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firm in Nigeria. Therefore, we conclude that the tax sheltering practices could be used to boost business growth opportunities and expansion in the listed

financial firms in Nigeria when practiced within the provisions of the law. These recommendations are derived from the findings:

- i. The effective tax rate of the financial firms should be monitored in relation to the statutory tax rate to ensure that it does not increase significantly.
- ii. The book tax difference should be monitored to ensure that the Gap does not widen significantly. Albeit insignificant, the negative direction of the effect is a cause for concerns which must be mitigated by effective tax planning policies.
- iii. Financial firms in Nigeria must make frantic efforts to minimize the book tax difference through tax sheltering.

REFERENCES

- Adegbite, T. A. & Shittu, S. A. (2017). The Analysis of the Impact of Corporate Income Tax on Investment in Nigeria. *World Wide Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 3(3), 60-64.
- Anyaduba, J. O., & Ogbeide, I. V. (2022). Firm attributes and corporate tax aggressiveness: a comparative study of Nigeria and South Africa banks. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 11(2), 18-34.
- Blaylock, B., Shevlin, T. & Wilson, R. J. (2012). Tax avoidance, large positive temporary book-tax differences, and earnings persistence. *The Accounting Review*, 82(1), 91-120.
- Delgado, F. J., FernandezQRodriguez, E., Garciau Fernandez, R. & MartinezD Arias, A. (2023). Tax avoidance and earnings management: a neural network approach for the largest European economies. *Financial Innovation* 9(19), 1-25.
- Desai, M. A. & Dharmapala, D. (2006). Corporate tax avoidance and high-powered incentives, *Journal of financial Economics*, 79, 145-179.
- Dyreg, S. D., Hanlon, M., & Maydew, E. L. (2010). The effects of executives on corporate tax avoidance. *Accounting Review*, 85(4), 63-89.
- Dyreg, S. D. & Maydew, E. L. (2018) Virtual issue on tax research, *J Account Res*, 56(1). 3-4.
- Gilang, L. & Wahya, D. (2022). The effect of corporate social responsibility on tax aggressiveness. *Saudi Journal of Economics and Finance*, 5(11), 476-481.
- Gilang, N. & Wahya, K. (2022). Effect of corporate social responsibility on tax aggressiveness. *Managerial Finance Journal*, 41(12), 1318-1335.
- Hanlon, M. & Heitzman, S. (2010), A review of tax research, *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 127-178.
- Igbru, O., Ukachi, M. T., & Ike, O. M. (2025). Characteristics of risk management committee and the earning capacity of listed deposit money banks in Africa. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Technology*, 10(5), 3062-3071.
- Igbru, O. & Orife, C. O. (2024). Effect of tax avoidance on firm value of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. *Unizik Journal*, 61(7), 302-317.
- Igbru, O., Nkechi, J. I., & Evi, P. (2023). Corporate risk management disclosure and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, (IJBFR) 9(4), 53-77.
- Ingrid, P. (2017). The effect of book-tax differences and corporate governance disclosure on the quality of earnings using accounting conservatism as moderating variables. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*. 13 (1) 32 - 37.
- Karami, R., Vaez, S. A. & Rekabdar, G. (2020). The impact of effective corporate governance on the relationship between tax gap and future profit changes in Iranian economy. *Advances in mathematical finance & applications*, 5(4), (2020), 491-505.
- Kim, J., L, Y. & Zhang, L. (2011). Corporate tax avoidance and stock price crash risk, Firm-level analysis. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 700(3), 639-662.
- Kportorgbi, H. K., Gadzo, S. G. & Gatsi, J. G. (2018). Corporate tax planning practice: a Bourdiesian's perspective. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 8(4), 208-226.
- Kumbour, A. N. & Demetia (2017). *Taxation in Ghana: Principles and Practice*. Accra: Black mask publication.
- Lanis, R. & Richardson, G. (2012). The effect of board of director composition on corporate tax aggressiveness *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 30, 50-70.
- Lanis, R. & Richardson G., (2012) "Corporate social responsibility and tax aggressiveness: An empirical analysis" *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 31(1) 86-108.
- Lee, B. B., Dobiyski, A. & Minton, S. (2015). Theories and empirical proxies for corporate tax avoidance. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 77(3), 21 - 33.
- Manzon, G. B. & Plesko, G. A. (2002) The Relation between financial and tax reporting measures of income. *Tax Law Review*, 55(1), 175-214.

- Martinez, A. L., Filho, I. D. & Anunciacao, E. P. (2013). Analysis of the relationship between the components of book-tax differences and annual variations in earnings and tax expenses of firms listed on the BMP & BOVESPA. *Advances in Scientific and Applied Accounting*. Sao Pew to. 1(3). 396-417.
- Martinez, A. L. & Rodrigues, A.M. (2019). The effect of corporate diversification on tax aggressiveness in Brazilian companies. *Contabilidade Gesiao e Governanca*, Z(1), 38-55. <https://doi.org/10.21714/1984-3925.2020v23nla3>
- Martinez, A. L. & DeSouza, T. B. T. (2015). Book-tax differences, earnings persistence and tax planning before and after the adoption of IFRS in Brazil *IX Congresso anpconl*, 31(03).1-18.
- Muhammad, D. ETTY. U. and Khomsiyah. K. (2020). The empirical evidence about the influence of lax aggressiveness, and managerial ownership to the Firm Value. *American Journal of Business and Management*, 2(3). 204-209.
- Muhammad, G. Wiwik, I. & Muluini. B. (2020). The influence of good corporate governance on tax aggressiveness. *SIT Journal of Management*. 10(2), 15-175.
- Moon, T. S. (2019) Capital gains taxes and real corporate investment. *Department of Economics and Industrial Relations Section, Princeton University, 248 Louis Simpson International Building, Princeton, NJ, 08544* 1 - 92.
- Nicholson, G. & Kiel, G. (2004). Breakthrough board performance: how to harness your board's intellectual capital, *Corporate Governance: The International of Business in Society*. 4(1), 5-23.
- Obasi, J. O., Okoye, E & Ifurueze, M. (2020). Tax aggressiveness and corporate investment expenditure in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Business and Social Sciences*. 3(2), 130 -140.
- Ogbeide, S. O. & Iyafekhe, C. (2018). Empirical assessment of tax aggressiveness of listed firms in Nigeria. *Accounting & Taxation Review*, 2(3), 13-29.
- Ogbo, E. C., Aladei, G. A. & Chime, U. A. (2026). Permanent book tax difference and corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firm in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 14(1), 279-292.
- Ogbo, E. C., Chime, U. A. & Aladei, G. A. (2026). Effect of tax sheltering on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative finance and Economics research*, 14(1), 438-451.
- Ogunmakin, A. A., Adebayo, A. I., Akinleye, M. J. & Anifowose, O. D. (2020). Tax avoidance and financial performance of quoted firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Management*, 10 (1), 47-54.
- Olurankinse, F. & Mamidu, A. S. (2021). Corporate tax planning and financial performance of development banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 9 (5), 53-72.
- Osegbue, I. F., Nweze, A., Ifurueze, M., & Nwoye, C. M. (2018). Effects of tax sheltering on earnings management in Nigeria. *Research Papers in Economics and Finance*, 3 (2), 43-69.
- Osegbue, I. F., Obasi, J. O., John-Akamelu, C R & Nwoye, C. M. (2021). Corporate tax aggressiveness and corporate investment expenditure in Nigeria and Ghana. *Econometric Research in Finance*, 6(2), 139-160.
- Oyeleke, O., Erin, O., & Emeni, F. (2016). Female directors and tax aggressiveness of listed banks in Nigeria. *3rd International Conference on African Development Issues (CU-ICADI 2016)* 293-299.
- Pereira, A., Pereira, C., Gomes, L. & Lima, A. (2022). Do taxes still affect earning persistence? *Administrative Sciences*, 73(48), 1-13.
- Rego, S. O. (2003). Tax-avoidance activities of U.S. multinational corporations. *Contemporary-Accounting Research*, 20(4), 805-833.
- Seidman, J. K. (2008). Investigating the book-tax income gap: factors which affect the gap and details regarding its most significant component. *A PhD thesis in Presented to the Department of Management, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*.
- Sulistyowati, D. & Hendrauati. k. (2018). The effect of book-tax differences on earnings growth. Karnings growth is measured using changes in net profit after tax. *International Journal of Accounting, Banking and Finance*, 9(3), 52-65.
- Udochukwu, G. O., Uniamikogbo, E. & Ezeji, A. M. (2022). Effect of managerial ownership and tax aggressiveness on financial performance of domestic systematically important banks in Nigeria. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*. (10), 51 -71.
- Zemzem, A. & Ftouhi, K. (2013). The effects of board of directors' characteristics on tax aggressiveness. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(4), 140-147